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Non-human primate reservoirs of zoonotic malaria infection: an underappreciated barrier to malaria eradication?

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Key points

- The origins of human malaria parasites—including *Plasmodium falciparum* and *P. vivax*—have been traced to non-human primate reservoirs, which harbor diverse assemblages of related parasites.
- Non-human primate malaria parasites exhibit considerable variation in zoonotic potential, and contemporary cross-species transmission of several species—including *P. knowlesi*, *P. simium*, and *P. brasilianum*—continues to this day.
- Efforts to quantify the risk that simian malaria parasites pose to human populations, and by extension malaria elimination, demand a holistic approach to zoonotic disease emergence that considers both ecological and molecular barriers to cross-species transmission.
- Ecological variables tend to govern the probability of human exposure to the zoonotic parasite and include the incidence of infection in the reservoir, the host biting preferences of the mosquito vector, and the degree of spatial overlap between human and reservoir host populations.
- Although molecular barriers to cross-species transmission could arise from any stage of the *Plasmodium* lifecycle, recent studies have implicated the process of erythrocyte invasion as a primary determinant of host-specificity.
- Flexible usage of redundant invasion pathways enables malaria parasites to overcome host barriers to infection.
- Non-human primates can be divided into three host clades: (1) apes, (2) Old World monkeys, and (3) New World monkeys. Malaria parasites of all three clades remain chronically understudied in the context of malaria elimination.
- African great apes are distributed throughout forested regions in equatorial Africa. The ape *Laverania* (i.e., relatives of *P. falciparum*) are highly host-restricted, likely the result of strong molecular barriers. The *Laverania* appear to pose little risk of emergence on contemporary timescales. In contrast, ape *P. vivax* isolates transcend species barriers more promiscuously. Although many humans in equatorial Africa are genetically resistant to *P. vivax*, those that express the Duffy Antigen Receptor for Chemokines may be susceptible. Emerging evidence of Duffy negative *P. vivax* invasion should be monitored closely. Apes also harbor parasites closely related to *P. ovale* and *P. malariae*, though more

work will be necessary to infer the directionality of transmission (i.e., apes-to-humans, humans-to-apes, or a combination thereof).

- Old World monkeys are widely distributed throughout tropical regions in Africa and Asia, and some species live in close proximity to humans. Although most malaria parasites of Old World monkeys appear to pose little material threat to humans, *P. knowlesi*—a zoonotic parasite of macaque monkeys—now constitutes the primary cause of malaria in parts of Southeast Asia. Although there is currently no unequivocal evidence of human-to-human *P. knowlesi* transmission, subsequent parasite adaptation to the human host could facilitate emergence on larger geographic scales. The increasing incidence of *P. knowlesi* in regions of Malaysia where control efforts have achieved success should be monitored closely. Despite a recent report of a human infection caused by *P. cynomolgi*, another macaque parasite, cross-species transmission of this parasite appears to be rare.
- New World monkeys are widely distributed in tropical forests in Central and South America. These reservoir hosts appear to harbor only two malaria parasites—*P. simium* and *P. brasilianum*, which are closely related to *P. vivax* and *P. malariae*, respectively. *Plasmodium simium* and *P. brasilianum* emerged in New World monkey populations less than 500 years ago following transmission from humans. These parasites appear to have retained the capacity to infect human hosts. Natural human infections have recently been documented, including a *P. simium* outbreak in a region of Brazil where malaria had been eliminated for over 50 years. It is critical that malaria elimination campaigns devote resources to evaluate the generalizability of this finding to other regions in South America.
- As malaria control efforts inch closer toward regional elimination, the relative impact of non-human primate malaria reservoirs will only increase. During ensuing years, it will be critical to discriminate between simian malaria parasites that pose a high risk of emergence (e.g., *P. knowlesi*, *P. simium*) from those that do not (e.g., the ape *Laverania*).
- Moving forward, it is critical that we adopt a holistic view of zoonotic disease emergence to evaluate the risk that simian malaria parasites pose to human populations. Longitudinal sampling of high-risk human populations, primate reservoirs, and mosquito vectors will offer measures of zoonotic incidence and exposure. Studies of molecular barriers will benefit from the recent generation of immortalized erythroid progenitor cell lines, which offer genetically tractable *in vitro* culture systems for the study of host-specificity. Mathematical models of malaria zoonosis will be necessary to link transmission dynamics across these disparate scales of analysis.

Summary

Malaria remains a potent source of global mortality and morbidity despite the success of control efforts during recent decades¹. While the vast majority of human malaria cases are caused by four parasites—*Plasmodium falciparum*, *P. vivax*, *P. malariae*, and *P. ovale*²—these species constitute less than 1% of the malaria parasite diversity found in the natural world. Indeed, over 500 malaria parasites circulate among avian, reptilian, and mammalian hosts³, many of which are incapable of replicating in humans. However, the expansion of human populations into biodiversity hotspots has elevated exposure to novel malaria parasites, a subset of which do possess the capacity to circumvent barriers to human infection. This paradigm is underscored by the growing health burden posed by *P. knowlesi*, a parasite of macaque monkeys, which now accounts for over 70% of human malaria infections in parts of Southeast Asia^{4,5}.

Recent advances in molecular diagnostics and expanded sampling of wild primate populations have revealed that *P. knowlesi* is not the only malaria parasite to transcend species boundaries. The precivilization origins of both *P. falciparum*^{6,7} and *P. vivax*^{8,9}—pandemic malaria parasites, which underlie the majority of human malaria infections globally^{1,2}—have been traced to African great apes (i.e., chimpanzees and gorillas). *Plasmodium malariae* and *P. ovale* have also been isolated from African great ape hosts (though the directionality of transmission remains unclear)^{6,10–12}, and primate-to-human transmission of other malaria parasites continues to this day (**Figure 1**). Given the taxonomic diversity of malaria hosts, the observation that most (if not all) human malaria parasites originated in our closest evolutionary relatives is striking and has compelled the scientific and public health communities to ask whether non-human primate reservoirs could impede malaria control efforts by acting as a source of recurrent human infection^{13–18}.

Although these findings demonstrate that non-human primate malaria parasites have the capacity to emerge in human populations on evolutionary timescales, the threat that these pathogens pose to contemporary public health is less clear. Primate-to-human transmission is generally rare and most malaria parasites must overcome substantial barriers to infect human hosts (**Figure 2**). However, recent studies have begun to highlight important exceptions to this rule. Advances in molecular diagnostics have revealed that at least three malaria parasites—*P. knowlesi*^{4,5}, *P. simium*^{19,20}, and *P. brasilianum*^{21,22}—appear to transcend human barriers promiscuously. Other simian parasites—*P. cynomolgi*²³ and ape *P. vivax*⁹—have also been isolated from human hosts. Finally, more work will be necessary to evaluate whether *P. malariae* and *P. ovale* infections of African great apes are capable of zoonotic transmission.

This body of evidence establishes a public health imperative to critically evaluate the drivers of variation in host restriction among malaria parasites in order to identify which species, if any, pose a material threat to human populations. The purpose of this report is to review current evidence concerning the zoonotic potential of non-human primate malaria parasites to facilitate evaluation of the extent to which these pathogens may act as a potential barrier to malaria eradication. To achieve this goal, I have divided this report into two parts.

In Part I, I provide background information pertaining to zoonotic disease emergence and the barriers to cross-species transmission. I first frame the discussion by offering a conceptual description of zoonotic disease emergence in the context of malaria cross-species transmission. I then discuss the interplay between ecological and molecular barriers to human infection by these zoonotic parasites.

In Part II, I discuss the diversity of non-human primate malaria parasites in the context of zoonotic disease emergence. First, I review historical and contemporary evidence of malaria cross-species transmission by focusing on three high-risk reservoir host clades—apes, Old World monkeys, and New World monkeys. I then conclude by highlighting key gaps in our understanding of these processes and briefly propose several productive avenues for future inquiry that must precede a formal policy recommendation.

Figure 1 | Evolutionary relationships of primate malaria parasites. Neighbor-joining tree was derived from a 3486-bp gapped mtDNA alignment encompassing the cytochrome oxidase subunit 3, cytochrome oxidase subunit 1-like, and cytochrome b genes of 24 previously published non-human primate malaria parasite sequences and outgroup *P. gallinaceum* (GenBank accession numbers: AB354571-AB354575, AB434918, AB434919, AB444136, AB489194, AJ251941, AY791692, AY800109, AY800110, EU880499, FJ895307, GQ355477, GQ355484, HM235302, HM235369, HM235379, HQ712054, JF923761, JQ308531, and NC_008288). Lineages are colored corresponding to geographic origin of host species (blue=South America; green=Africa; orange=Asia). Human-adapted lineages, which are globally distributed, are colored red. Lineages are labeled according to host species and degree of specificity for the human host in natural settings. Figure adapted from Scully et al.²⁴

PART I

Zoonotic disease emergence and the barriers to cross-species transmission of non-human primate malaria parasites

A zoonotic disease (or zoonosis) is an infectious disease transmitted from an animal population (i.e., a “zoonotic reservoir”) to a human host^{25–27}. Researchers have estimated that nearly two thirds of contemporary human pathogens—including HIV, influenza, and other prominent human pandemics—have zoonotic origins^{27–30}. While twentieth century public health campaigns have successfully controlled the proliferation of chronic human pathogens ranging from smallpox to polio, the rate of zoonotic disease emergence has increased over this period^{25,27,31}. During recent decades, the expansion of human populations into biodiversity hotspots has precipitated the emergence of SARS, MERS, Ebola, H1N1 influenza, and numerous other zoonotic outbreaks of public health relevance^{31–35}. As malaria control efforts approach regional elimination, the public health community should critically evaluate whether zoonotic malaria parasites pose a similar risk of emergence. In this section, I introduce the zoonotic spectrum as a conceptual framework to structure the discussion of the zoonotic potential of non-human primate malaria parasites.

The zoonotic spectrum

The process of zoonotic disease emergence is typically conceptualized as an adaptive continuum, whereby parasites are classified into one of three stages: parasites transmissible within the animal reservoir (Stage 1), parasites transmissible from animal to human (Stage 2), and parasites transmissible among humans (Stage 3)^{25–27}. The natural diversity of primate malaria parasites spans the zoonotic spectrum (**Figure 2**). Four malaria parasites (i.e., *P. falciparum*, *P. vivax*, *P. malariae*, *P. ovale*) have adapted to the human population and are transmissible among human hosts (i.e., Stage 3)². Most human malaria cases are attributable to these parasites. In contrast, three non-human primate malaria parasites species (i.e., *P. knowlesi*^{4,5}, *P. simium*^{19,20}, *P. brasilianum*^{21,22}) have the capacity to infect human hosts but appear to be either incapable of human-to-human transmission or produce stuttering transmission chains in the human population (i.e., Stage 2). While several other species (i.e., *P. cynomolgi*²³, ape *P. vivax* lineages⁹) have also been isolated from human hosts, these events appear to be fairly rare. Emergence of these Stage 2 parasites may require further adaptation to the human host. Finally, most primate malaria parasites (e.g., the ape *Laverania*⁶) appear to be either incapable of crossing species boundaries or do so inefficiently (i.e., Stage 1). I discuss these zoonotic malaria parasites in greater depth in Part II of this report.

A pathogen’s position along the zoonotic spectrum is determined by its basic reproductive number (i.e., R_0) in the human host²⁵. Here, R_0 is defined as the average number of secondary cases that arise from an initial primary case in a wholly susceptible population³⁶. More simply, the R_0 value describes a pathogen’s capacity to persist within the host population and is a representation of the rate of transmission relative to the rate of recovery. If R_0 is less than one, the pathogen is incapable of sustained transmission within the human population and will eventually go extinct therein. By contrast, if R_0 is greater than one, the pathogen will emerge in the human population, yielding a sustained epidemic. While many zoonotic spillover events are either incapable of forward transmission ($R_0=0$, or Stage 1) or produce stuttering transmission chains that eventually burn out ($R_0<1$, or Stage 2), subsequent adaptation may permit efficient replication and transmission within the novel host population, yielding an evolutionary host shift ($R_0>1$, or Stage 3).

Both intrinsic characteristics of the pathogen (e.g., mode of transmission; transmission rate), as well as characteristics of the host population (e.g., social structure; population density) ultimately determine the R_0 value of an infectious disease. Because malaria is a vector-borne disease transmitted by *Anopheles* mosquitos, its R_0 value is influenced by interactions between (1) host and parasite (e.g., parasite virulence; human-to-mosquito infectiousness), (2) host and vector (e.g., host biting rate; ratio of mosquitos to human hosts), and (3) vector and parasite (e.g., mosquito lifespan; duration of parasite development within the mosquito; mosquito-to-human infectiousness)^{37–39}. By influencing R_0 , each of these parameters may form a barrier to cross-species transmission, thus determining a parasite’s zoonotic potential.

Figure 2 | The zoonotic spectrum. The process of zoonotic disease emergence is typically conceptualized as an adaptive continuum, whereby parasites are classified into one of three stages: parasites transmissible within the animal reservoir (Stage 1), parasites transmissible from animal to human (Stage 2), and parasites transmissible among humans (Stage 3)²⁵⁻²⁷. Malaria parasites of non-human primates span this zoonotic spectrum and, therefore, pose variable risks to contemporary human populations. Adaptation to the human host facilitates transition along the zoonotic spectrum. Figure adapted from Scully et al.²⁴.

Barriers to cross-species transmission: from the bush to the bench

In order to reproduce, the *Plasmodium* parasite must navigate a complex lifecycle that spans both vertebrate and invertebrate hosts². Following sexual replication in the midgut of an *Anopheles* mosquito, the asexual form of the *Plasmodium* parasite (i.e., the sporozoite) is transmitted to the vertebrate host via the bite of this insect vector. After an initial cycle of replication in the liver, the parasite emerges into the cardiovascular system in its blood-stage form, the merozoite. Repeated cycles of invasion, growth, and egress among erythrocytes enable the parasite to proliferate within the host and, ultimately, produce the clinical symptoms associated with infection. A subset of blood-stage parasites mature into sexual stage gametocytes, which complete the *Plasmodium* lifecycle upon ingestion by an *Anopheles* mosquito vector.

Although parasite-host incompatibility could theoretically result from restriction at any stage of the *Plasmodium* lifecycle, a parasite's zoonotic potential (i.e., the capacity of a parasite to transition from Stage 1 to Stage 2) is ultimately a function of two parameters: (1) the magnitude of human exposure to the novel parasite, and (2) the probability of human infection per exposure event. By extension, factors related to either the ecology of the parasite or the degree of molecular compatibility between host and parasite (or between vector and parasite) may constitute barriers to cross-species transmission. Accordingly, discrimination between these two classes of barriers is a critical step in the evaluation of the risk that a parasite poses to the human population.

Ecological barriers to cross-species transmission

The probability of cross-species transmission depends, in part, upon the magnitude of human exposure to the zoonotic parasite. Thus, environmental factors that mediate spatiotemporal variation in human exposure will tend to influence where and when a given parasite is likely to emerge. This information can be operationalized to identify hypothetical zoonotic transmission hotspots and design emerging infectious disease surveillance efforts^{27,31}. This section highlights three parameters that structure variation in exposure to zoonotic malaria parasites: (1) incidence of infection in the primate reservoir, (2) vector biting preferences, and (3) spatial overlap between human and reservoir hosts.

The magnitude of transmission in the animal reservoir shapes the probability of cross-species transmission by influencing the potential for ‘spillover’ exposure (i.e., incidental exposure of an alternative host to a novel parasite)²⁶. Ecological variables play a key role in structuring malaria transmission by influencing epidemiological parameters at the parasite-mosquito interface. For example, ambient temperature influences both the population dynamics of the mosquito vector and the rate of parasite development within the vector⁴⁰⁻⁴⁵. Similarly, precipitation influences transmission probability by mediating the availability of breeding habitat for aquatic larval mosquitoes (e.g., transitory oviposition sites)^{41,42,46}. Spatial variation in these ecological variables defines the suitability of a particular locale for malaria transmission, and temporal variation in this parameter accentuates the seasonality of infection. All else being equal, human exposure is most likely to occur in hotspots that are particularly conducive to transmission within the animal reservoir.

While the magnitude of transmission within the animal reservoir is one factor that structures human exposure risk, this parameter must be considered in tandem with the biting preferences of the mosquito vector. Logically, parasites transmitted by vectors that promiscuously feed upon both humans and non-human primates will pose a greater zoonotic exposure risk than will those transmitted by mosquitoes that have strict host preferences. Unfortunately, the extent to which many *Anopheline* vectors discriminate among humans and non-human primates largely remains unclear. A number of studies have classified particular vectors as either anthrophilic (i.e., human-biting preference) and zoophilic (i.e., animal-biting preference), based largely upon the proportion of blood meals taken from humans and livestock, respectively^{47,48}. However, vectors may not discriminate between the chemical cues of humans and our closest evolutionary relatives to the same degree. For example, Gabonese vectors of ape parasites (i.e., *An. vinckei*, *An. moucheti*, and *An. marshallii*) do bite humans when given the opportunity⁴⁹ even though *An. vinckei* had previously been classified as strictly zoophilic⁵⁰. The nuanced biting preferences of *An. vinckei* underscores the relevance of ecological context in evaluating zoonotic potential.

Finally, spatial overlap between human and reservoir populations is a critical pre-requisite for zoonotic exposure. In many tropical regions, humans and non-human primates live in close proximity, offering myriad opportunities for vector-borne transmission^{51,52}. While many infectious zoonotic pathogens require direct contact for transmission (e.g., simian retroviruses and bushmeat consumption^{51,53-55}), exposure to a zoonotic malaria parasite only requires that the human host live close enough to the primate reservoir to be within the flight range of the vector. For example, a history of forest contact is a critical risk factor for human exposure to the zoonotic macaque parasite, *P. knowlesi*^{56,57}. In contrast, humans that do not interface with these forests are less susceptible to infection.

In summary, zoonotic exposure is most likely to occur where humans live in close proximity to primates that harbor a high incidence of malaria infection, which is transmitted by *Anopheline* vectors that exhibit promiscuous biting preferences. The identification of these zoonotic exposure hotspots will require careful consideration of the broader ecological context in which these interactions occur.

Molecular barriers to cross-species transmission

Given a sufficient magnitude of exposure, molecular factors may present additional barriers to emergence by influencing the efficiency of parasite replication and transmission among human hosts. Although all stages of the complex *Plasmodium* lifecycle (reviewed elsewhere²) offer opportunities for molecular incompatibility, most remain chronically understudied in the context of host-specificity. In

particular, species barriers to liver stage infection and molecular incompatibilities between parasite and mosquito vector constitute important avenues for future research.

Most research concerning the host-specificity of primate malaria parasites has focused upon host-parasite interactions occurring in the context of the red blood cell. The process of erythrocyte invasion is comprised of an ordered sequence of molecular interactions between parasite ligands expressed upon the surface of the invasive merozoite and host receptors expressed upon the surface of the erythrocyte membrane. Although much of this discussion is beyond the scope of this report, I highlight two parasite protein families that play a prominent role in host tropism: (1) the erythrocyte binding-like (EBL) proteins and (2) the reticulocyte binding like (RBL) proteins⁵⁸⁻⁶⁰. Each EBL and RBL protein binds specifically to a receptor expressed upon the surface of the erythrocyte, irreversibly committing the parasite to invasion⁵⁹. Because all malaria pathogenesis is attributable to complications of blood stage infection, evolutionary pressures have selected for red blood cell heterogeneities that likely contribute to host restriction.

Given the magnitude of the selective pressure imposed by malaria pathogenesis during recent human evolution, it is perhaps unsurprising that proteins associated with the red blood cell constitute primary targets of parasite-induced selection^{61,62}. Indeed, quintessential examples of molecular evolution in humans (e.g., sickle-cell anemia, Duffy-negativity, G6PD deficiency) are attributable to selection for polymorphisms that protect against severe malaria^{61,63}. As a result of these selective pressures, many receptors of the EBL and RBL ligands exhibit considerable genetic diversity both within and among host species⁶⁴⁻⁶⁶.

A growing body of evidence suggests that malaria parasites have adapted to this host cell heterogeneity via an evolutionary expansion of the EBL and RBL gene families. All *Plasmodium* species for which genomes have been sequenced encode multiple EBL and RBL proteins. While genetic variation in the EBL and RBL protein families has been implicated in immune evasion⁶⁷, these gene expansions also offer a degree of plasticity in host cell invasion by enabling the parasite to use multiple alternative ligand-receptor interactions—known as invasion pathways—for host cell entry. In the following sections, I highlight the role that this adaptive mechanism plays in host-specificity.

PART II

The zoonotic potential of non-human primate malaria parasites

The primate order is composed of over 500 species in ~70 genera, which shared a common ancestor between 76 and 99 million years ago⁶⁸. Although non-human primates are distributed throughout tropical and sub-tropical regions of Africa, Asia, South America, and Central America, over 60% of these species currently face the threat of extinction⁶⁹. This threatened status is largely attributable to the rapid expansion of human populations during recent decades, which has occurred at the expense of primate habitat. As patterns of human encroachment on the habitats of non-human primates intensify, there is little doubt that novel zoonotic pathogens will continue to emerge. This section seeks to identify the non-human primate malaria parasites that pose the greatest threat to human populations during ensuing decades.

The primate order can be sub-divided into two major groups: (1) prosimian primates (lemurs, lorises, and tarsiers), and (2) anthropoid primates (apes, Old World monkeys, and New World monkeys). Although prosimian malaria parasites have been described previously⁷⁰, this section focuses exclusively upon parasites of anthropoid primates. Indeed, although over 500 avian, reptilian, and mammalian malaria parasites have been described³, only anthropoid primate reservoirs are known to harbor malaria parasites capable of infecting humans. In the following sections, we describe the malaria parasites of three anthropoid primate clades—apes, Old World monkeys, and New World monkeys—and discuss the extent to which the emergence of these pathogens poses a threat to malaria eradication.

Malaria parasites of apes

As our closest evolutionary relatives, humans and apes (superfamily: *Hominoidea*) share a high degree

of molecular and cellular homology, which has engendered a general predisposition to cross-species pathogen exchange on contemporary timescales⁷¹⁻⁷³. Taxonomically, the apes are comprised of the Hylobatids (i.e., gibbons and siamangs, endemic to Southeast Asia), orangutans (endemic to Borneo and Sumatra), and African great apes (i.e., chimpanzees, gorillas, bonobos, and humans). Although malaria parasites of Hylobatids and orangutans have been described previously⁷⁴⁻⁷⁷, very little is known about their ecology, epidemiology, and molecular biology. Additionally, malaria parasitism of wild bonobos has not yet been described^{6,8}. Future work will be necessary to evaluate whether these primate species constitute relevant zoonotic reservoirs.

In this section, I focus upon malaria parasites of African great apes (i.e., chimpanzees and gorillas). Humans diverged from chimpanzees and gorillas less than seven million and nine million years ago, respectively⁶⁸. Although both chimpanzees and gorillas are endemic to equatorial Africa, chimpanzees occupy a significantly wider habitat range⁷⁸. During the last decade, non-invasive surveys of African great ape fecal samples have revealed that chimpanzees and gorillas harbor diverse assemblages of malaria parasites, which vary considerably in their zoonotic potential. In the following sections, I focus upon three groups of African great ape malaria parasites: (1) relatives of *P. falciparum* (i.e., the *Laverania* sub-genus), (2) relatives of *P. vivax*, and (3) other African great ape malaria parasites (i.e., relatives of *P. malariae* and *P. ovale*).

Plasmodium falciparum and the *Laverania*: a highly host restricted clade of malaria parasites

Plasmodium falciparum is the most prevalent and malignant human malaria parasite, responsible for 200 million cases and 400,000 deaths annually, primarily in sub-Saharan Africa^{1,79}. Non-invasive sampling of wild primates has revealed that the origin of *P. falciparum* is traceable to a sub-genus of African great ape malaria parasites, known as the *Laverania*^{6,7} (**Figure 1**). *Plasmodium falciparum* isolates collected from across the globe form a single monophyletic clade embedded within the diversity of a gorilla parasite, which has been deemed *P. praefalciparum*⁶. This pattern strongly suggests that the human *P. falciparum* pandemic emerged from a single gorilla-to-human cross-species transmission event ~50,000 years ago⁸⁰, preceding the expansion of humans out of Africa.

Despite the zoonotic origin of *P. falciparum*, a defining feature of the *Laverania* is the high degree of contemporary host-specificity that these parasites exhibit. The *Laverania* cluster into host species-specific clades with little evidence of cross-species transmission, despite geographical overlap in host distributions^{6,17,18}. Given that the *Laverania* are highly prevalent in African great ape populations⁶ and mosquito vectors of these parasites readily bite humans⁴⁹, it is likely that human exposure occurs with regularity in parts of equatorial Africa. These observations suggest that barriers to cross-species transmission of the *Laverania* are primarily molecular, rather than ecological. However, some human-to-ape and primate-to-primate transmission has been documented in captive environments^{12,81-83}, demonstrating that these barriers may be porous under particular epidemiological scenarios.

The extensive repertoire of *P. falciparum* EBL and RBL invasion ligands offers a high degree of functional redundancy during human erythrocyte invasion. Although it was traditionally believed that no single ligand was necessary for erythrocyte invasion by all *P. falciparum* strains, functional experiments have since identified Rh5 as an essential determinant of erythrocyte invasion⁸⁴⁻⁸⁶. Polymorphism in the Rh5 ligand underlies variation in binding affinity to the erythrocytes of *Aotus* monkeys, suggesting that this ligand may also be an important determinant of host preferences⁸⁶. The Rh5 receptor was subsequently identified to be the Ok blood group protein, Basigin (BSG)⁸⁷.

These findings have since spurred researchers to test the hypothesis that variation in Rh5 affinity for non-human primate BSG proteins underlies the strong affinity of *P. falciparum* for human red blood cells. Indeed, the *P. falciparum* Rh5 ligand binds to human BSG with ten-fold greater affinity relative to the chimpanzee protein and does not bind to gorilla BSG, an effect attributable to several amino acid substitutions in non-human primate BSG proteins⁸⁸. Several of these amino acid residues have undergone positive selection in great apes, and an Rh5 residue that stabilizes the interaction with BSG has been positively selected in *P. falciparum*⁸⁹. These findings suggest that a co-evolutionary arms race between Rh5 and BSG structures the host preferences of *P. falciparum*. Future studies must determine whether this

mechanism reciprocally governs the host-specificity of its zoonotic relatives.

Moving forward, erythrocyte invasion assays will be necessary to identify other molecular barriers to cross-species transmission. For example, while Rh5-BSG forms the foundation for *Laveranian* host tropism, it is conceivable that invasion is enhanced by other receptor-ligand interactions. The recently sequenced genomes of the ape *Laverania*^{80,90} are likely to offer novel insights. In particular, the hypothesis that pseudogenization of the *PfRh3* and *PfEBA165* ligands and/or duplication of *PfRh2* were necessary prerequisites for expression of alternative, human-permissive invasion pathways warrants further investigation.

Additionally, although two previous surveys of humans living in Gabon and Cameroon have failed to identify zoonotic *Laverania* infections^{17,18}, more intensive sampling of human populations living in exposure hotspots will be necessary to confidently rule out low levels of cross-species transmission. Indeed, while there is no evidence of human-to-ape transmission of *P. falciparum* in the wild, the high levels of *P. falciparum* exposure that apes experience in captivity is sufficient for human-to-ape transmission^{12,81–83}. It remains unclear whether the converse (i.e., ape-to-human transmission in the context of elevated exposure) also occurs in parts of equatorial Africa. Efforts to quantify the ecological drivers of spatiotemporal transmission within great ape reservoirs will be necessary to identify hypothetical transmission hotspots (**Figure 3**). Finally, next-generation sequencing methods that more intensively sample the within-host diversity of human infections will be necessary to eliminate the possibility that zoonotic transmission has been masked by *P. falciparum* co-infection.

While there is much work to be done, the current body of evidence suggests that the ape *Laverania* pose little or no risk to human populations given the high degree of host-specificity that these species exhibit.

Figure 3 | Mapping spatiotemporal variation in *Laverania* infection in wild chimpanzee reservoirs. This risk map articulates spatiotemporal variation in the predicted probability that a chimpanzee fecal sample will test positive for *Laverania* infection. Infection probabilities were derived from a binomial generalized linear mixed model, which included ambient temperature, rainfall, and forest cover as predictor variables. Model was parameterized using 2,436 chimpanzee fecal samples collected from 55 field sites across equatorial Africa. Samples were screened for *Plasmodium* mtDNA using methods described previously⁶. Note that infection probabilities are independent of human and chimpanzee population density. Figure adapted from Scully et al. (in preparation).

Plasmodium vivax: a long neglected pandemic

Plasmodium vivax accounts for ~50% of all human malaria cases outside of Africa¹. Once believed to have emerged from macaque monkeys^{91,92}, improved sampling of non-human primates has revealed that this pandemic actually originated in African great apes⁸. Indeed, human *P. vivax* isolates form a monophyletic clade embedded within the diversity of closely related ape parasites. Though this pattern is superficially reminiscent of *P. falciparum*'s relationship to the ape *Laverania*, *P. vivax* appears to transcend species boundaries more promiscuously. First, *P. vivax* is readily transmissible between chimpanzees and gorillas⁸, while the ape *Laverania* form host-specific clades⁶. Second, though rare, ape-to-human *P. vivax* transmission has recently been reported in Central Africa⁹.

The interaction between the *P. vivax* invasion ligand, PvDBP, and its host receptor, the Duffy antigen/receptor for chemokines (DARC), has long been thought to be an essential determinant of *P. vivax* invasion^{93,94}. Indeed, *P. vivax* pathogenicity has favored the proliferation of a mutation in the DARC promoter, which abrogates expression of this protein on human erythrocytes^{94,95}. This DARC-null allele, which arose less than 33,000 years ago⁹⁶, can now be found at >95% frequency in parts of sub-Saharan Africa and is thought to underlie the near complete absence of *P. vivax* in human populations on the African continent⁹⁷. However, evidence of DARC-null *P. vivax* invasion has begun to accumulate in recent years⁹⁸⁻¹⁰³, the mechanistic basis of which is a source of current debate^{104,105}. Given the important public health implications of these findings for the spread of *P. vivax* in Africa, evaluation of these hypotheses will prove to be a productive avenue for future inquiry. However, functional assays will be necessary to test these hypotheses, and progress may be slow until a continuous *in vitro* *P. vivax* culture system is developed¹⁰⁶.

Because the ape origin of *P. vivax* has only been described recently^{8,9}, the functional determinants of ape *P. vivax* host-specificity remain largely unexplored. Nevertheless, it has been proposed that the DARC-null phenotype restricts ape-to-human *P. vivax* transmission within equatorial Africa⁸. If ape *P. vivax* does, indeed, require expression of the DARC allele for human erythrocyte invasion, then these parasites likely pose a low risk to human populations overall. In this scenario, only travelers and DARC-positive Africans would face recurrent infection risks. Indeed, the only previous report of ape-to-human *P. vivax* transmission involved a Caucasian (i.e., DARC-positive) traveler, who spent 18 days working in a forest in the Central African Republic⁹.

However, the great ape reservoir warrants careful consideration in light of the emerging body of evidence concerning DARC-null *P. vivax* invasion. Reports of *P. vivax* outbreaks in equatorial Africa are striking¹⁰⁷, and several recent studies conducted in countries harboring African great apes have isolated *P. vivax* from Duffy-negative individuals^{101,103,108}. While it is possible that we have underestimated the magnitude of human-to-human *P. vivax* transmission within Africa, these observations also raise the possibility that ape reservoirs are continuously seeding infections to the human population. Additional phylogenetic analyses that encompass a greater diversity of ape and African human isolates will be necessary to discriminate between these two hypotheses.

Other parasites of African great apes

Non-invasive sampling of wild African great apes has demonstrated that chimpanzees and gorillas also harbor malaria parasites very closely related to *P. malariae* and *P. ovale*^{6,10-12}. Is it possible that the origins of all four human-adapted malaria parasites are traceable to our closest evolutionary relatives? Although this hypothesis is compelling¹⁵, such an assertion is premature and further analysis will be necessary to reach a formal conclusion.

Three distinct hypotheses could explain the isolation of *P. malariae* and *P. ovale* from both human and African great ape hosts. First, it is possible that human infections are, indeed, the result of ancient and/or contemporary zoonoses of ape origin. In this scenario, malaria control efforts should carefully consider the ape reservoir as a potential source of ongoing human *P. malariae* and *P. ovale* infection. Second, it is conceivable that these ape infections are anthroponotic (i.e., transmitted from human to ape). Given that anthroponotic pathogens constitute a major source of mortality among wild apes¹⁰⁹⁻¹¹¹, this finding would hold significant relevance to the conservation of these endangered primates. Third, it is possible that some *P. malariae* and *P. ovale* strains hold the capacity for promiscuous transmission among humans and apes. This possibility represents a 'worst-case scenario,' and would warrant consideration by both the public

health and wildlife conservation communities.

Several courses of action will facilitate discrimination among these possibilities. Because few ape *P. ovale* and *P. malariae* isolates have been sequenced, more intensive sampling of a wider geographic distribution of humans and apes in Africa must precede further analysis. Subsequent phylogenetic analysis of these isolates will be necessary to evaluate the degree to which human and ape strains are inter-mixed (an indicator of cross-species transmission). Finally, comparison of the genetic diversity of human and ape isolates will enable researchers to infer whether apes constitute a reservoir of human infection or vice versa.

The public health community has largely overlooked *P. ovale* and *P. malariae* due to the relative obscurity of these parasites. However, as efforts to control *P. falciparum* and *P. vivax* inch closer to regional elimination, these neglected tropical diseases may begin to factor more prominently into policy discussions. The recent sequencing of the *P. ovale* and *P. malariae* genomes constitutes an important first step in understanding the biology of these parasites¹¹². Inference of the magnitude of ape-to-human transmission will be necessary to further elucidate their epidemiological dynamics.

Malaria parasites of Old World monkeys

The Old World monkeys (OWMs) populate a diverse clade of over 130 species, which are distributed throughout the African and Asian tropics (**Figure 1**). OWMs diverged from the apes (including humans) between 20 and 27 million years ago⁶⁸. Because OWMs are more evolutionarily distant than the apes, malaria parasites that have adapted to the OWM cellular environment may be generally less capable of efficient replication in humans. Indeed, none of the human-adapted malaria parasites appear to have originated in OWM reservoirs, suggesting that molecular barriers may reduce human susceptibility to most OWM malaria parasites.

However, it is also likely that the magnitude of human exposure to OWM malaria parasites exceeds that of ape parasites. OWMs are more widely distributed than are apes, and some OWM species live in very close proximity to humans in both urban and rural environments. This high degree of close contact has facilitated the cross-species transmission of a number of OWM pathogens (e.g., Herpes B virus¹¹³). Indeed, two OWM species—long-tailed and pig-tailed macaques (*M. fascicularis* and *M. nemestrina*, respectively)—harbor *P. knowlesi*, the most important zoonotic malaria parasite of contemporary times. In this section, I discuss *P. knowlesi* zoonosis, and briefly highlight evidence for cross-species transmission of another macaque parasite, *P. cynomolgi*.

Monkey in the middle: the emerging public health threat posed by *P. knowlesi* zoonosis

Plasmodium knowlesi is a zoonotic malaria parasite of macaque monkeys, which is responsible for a growing number of human cases in Southeast Asia^{4,5}. Long mistaken for *P. malariae* due to its morphological similarity, molecular methods have since implicated zoonotic *P. knowlesi* in up to 70% of malaria infections in rural Malaysia^{4,5}. Interestingly, efforts to eliminate *P. falciparum* and *P. vivax* in Southeast Asia have coincided with an increase in the incidence of *P. knowlesi*, an effect that cannot be explained by elevated surveillance or improved molecular diagnosis methodology^{16,114}. Accordingly, *P. knowlesi* zoonosis constitutes a major hurdle to malaria eradication efforts in Southeast Asia and may represent a harbinger of future challenges in other geographic locations as zoonotic parasites compete to fill the host niche left by *P. falciparum* and *P. vivax*.

Although long-tailed macaques and pig-tailed macaques each harbor a high prevalence of *P. knowlesi* infection¹¹⁵, parasites of each reservoir species appear to be reproductively isolated¹¹⁶. While it remains unclear whether this parasite population structure stems from geographic isolation or molecular restriction, both clades are capable of infecting human hosts¹¹⁶. Although human-to-human *P. knowlesi* transmission has not been conclusively demonstrated in natural settings, this parasite produces gametocytes (i.e., transmission stages) in human blood, suggesting that larger outbreaks with human-to-human transmission are not inconceivable¹¹⁷. Nevertheless, the current body of evidence indicates that monkey-to-human transmission is the sole route of human *P. knowlesi* infection and that outbreaks will likely be confined to the geographic distribution of the macaque reservoir. On finer-grained spatial scales, changes in patterns of

land-use, such as deforestation, have been implicated as risk factors for *P. knowlesi* zoonosis⁵⁷. Adult males working in agricultural areas appear to be particularly susceptible to infection, suggesting that behavioral factors likely play an important role in exposure, as well⁵⁶.

Plasmodium knowlesi must also overcome a number of molecular barriers to infect human hosts. Sialic acids represent one such barrier to emergence. Sialic acids are acidic sugars that terminate glycan chains on vertebrate proteins^{118,119}. More simply, if the backbone of a protein can be likened to the trunk of a tree, sialic acids are analogous to its leaves. Two primary sialic acid variants are expressed on mammalian cells: N-acetylneuraminic acid (Neu5Ac) and N-glycolylneuraminic acid (Neu5Gc)^{118,119}. Neu5Ac is converted to Neu5Gc by the CMAH gene, which has been pseudogenized in the human lineage^{118,119}. Thus, Neu5Ac is the sole sialic acid variant found on human proteins, while Neu5Gc is the principal sialic acid of apes and Old World monkeys.

Because EBL ligands of many malaria parasites rely upon sialic acids for host cell binding, parasites adapted to hosts expressing Neu5Gc may invade cells expressing Neu5Ac less efficiently. Indeed, *P. knowlesi* preferentially invades cells expressing the OWM sialic acid, Neu5Gc. This pattern is driven by two EBL ligands—*PkDBP* β and *PkDBP* γ —which bind to erythrocytes expressing Neu5Gc, but not those expressing Neu5Ac¹²⁰. In contrast, a third ligand—*PkDBP* α —does not require sialic acids for host cell binding¹²⁰.

These results suggest that the usage of alternative invasion pathways underlies the affinity of zoonotic *P. knowlesi* for human erythrocytes. While sialic acid-dependent pathways (i.e., *PkDBP* β and *PkDBP* γ) appear to enhance *P. knowlesi* invasion efficiency in its natural simian host, the indifference of the *PkDBP* α pathway to sialic acid variant serves to bridge the fitness valley associated with the foreign cellular surface of the human red blood cell. Nevertheless, *P. knowlesi* invasion and replication is less efficient in human cells relative to macaque cells, indicating that further adaptation may be necessary for widespread emergence.

Expansion of *P. knowlesi*'s cellular niche in the human host may constitute one such adaptation¹²¹. Although invasion of most human malaria parasites is largely restricted to either younger reticulocytes (*P. vivax*¹²², *P. ovale*¹²³) or older normocytes (*P. malariae*¹²⁴), *P. falciparum* achieves elevated parasitemia via relaxation of this restriction¹²⁵. *In vitro* assays have demonstrated that while *P. knowlesi* is indifferent to the age of erythrocytes within the macaque host, invasion is limited to reticulocytes in humans¹²¹. However, *in vitro* adaptation of *P. knowlesi* has revealed that enhanced invasion of older erythrocytes via amplification of *PkDBP* α enables this parasite to achieve a marked increase in the rate of parasite proliferation in human blood^{121,120}.

These studies demonstrate that while multiple axes of host cell variation constitute potential barriers to emergence, the expression of redundant invasion pathways has endowed *P. knowlesi* with the functional toolkit necessary to circumvent this host restriction. As the incidence of *P. knowlesi* infection increases, additional research will be necessary to elucidate the compensatory ligand adaptations that underlie relaxation of reticulocyte restriction.

Other parasites of old world monkeys

Although a number of other malaria parasites of OWMs have been identified (**Figure 1**), few appear to be capable of infecting human hosts in natural settings. However, *P. cynomolgi* constitutes an interesting exception. *Plasmodium cynomolgi* is a macaque parasite closely related to *P. knowlesi*, which has recently been isolated from human hosts²³. Like *P. knowlesi*, *P. cynomolgi* invades macaque erythrocytes of all ages indiscriminately, but is reticulocyte-restricted in human blood, potentially limiting its zoonotic potential¹²⁶. Long-term *in vitro* culture of *P. cynomolgi* in human blood and comparison with *P. knowlesi* may reveal convergent mechanisms of adaptation to the human host and offer novel insight into the process of zoonotic emergence. For the time being, however, *P. cynomolgi* is unlikely to pose a major risk of recurrent human infection.

Malaria parasites of New World Monkeys

The New World monkeys (NWMs) occupy a clade of over 130 primate species, which are confined to the South and Central American tropics (**Figure 1**). NWMs diverged from the ancestor of OWMs and apes between 36 and 50 million years ago⁶⁸. Despite the greater phylogenetic distance, emerging evidence suggests that it is unsafe to assume that malaria parasites of NWMs pose a lesser threat to human populations than do those of OWMs and apes. Of particular note, the CMAH gene was independently pseudogenized in the ancestor of both NWMs and modern humans^{119,127}. Accordingly, while apes and OWMs express the Neu5Gc sialic acid variant upon cell surface proteins, humans and NWMs each express the Neu5Ac variant. Given that a number of erythrocyte invasion pathways depend upon sialic acids for host cell entry (discussed above), it is conceivable that this trait endows humans and NWMs with a similar cellular environment that is mutually permissive of cross-species pathogen exchange.

P. simium and P. brasilianum: simian parasites with underestimated zoonotic potential

Relative to OWMs and apes, the species richness of NWM malaria parasites is greatly reduced. In fact, only two species—*P. simium* and *P. brasilianum*—have heretofore been isolated from NWMs. While howler monkeys (*Alouatta* spp.) are a commonly cited reservoir of *P. simium* and *P. brasilianum*, these parasites have now been isolated from a wide range of wild NWM species, suggesting that these parasites can cross species barriers promiscuously^{128,129}. Future work will be necessary to comprehensively quantify the prevalence and distribution of these parasites within NWM reservoirs.

Phylogenetic analyses have revealed that *P. simium* is very closely related to *P. vivax*, while *P. brasilianum* is a close relative of *P. malariae* (**Figure 1**). Interestingly, patterns of phylogenetic clustering and genetic diversity suggest that each of these parasites likely emerged in NWM populations less than 500 years ago, the result of human-to-NWM cross-species transmission events^{15,130,131}. Now that these species have adapted to NWMs, a key question concerns whether these species have retained the capacity for human infection.

Despite limited sampling, both *P. simium* and *P. brasilianum* have now been isolated from human hosts^{19,20,22}. Because *P. simium* and *P. brasilianum* are morphologically indistinguishable from their human-adapted relatives, it is likely that the magnitude of monkey-to-human transmission of these parasites has been underestimated. Indeed, Brasil *et al.*²⁰ recently used a molecular assay to demonstrate that outbreaks of (presumed) *P. vivax* in Rio de Janeiro state, Brazil—where elimination had been achieved for over 50 years—are actually attributable to *P. simium*. If these zoonotic outbreaks are generalizable to other regions of South America^{19,20,129}, surveillance of NWM reservoirs will be an integral component of malaria control efforts in these regions. It will, therefore, be of central importance to invest in molecular epidemiological studies that quantify rates of zoonotic exposure and transmission in these regions to thoroughly quantify the magnitude of this underappreciated threat.

Potential impact on malaria eradication and areas for future research

Efforts to eliminate malaria from the human population have achieved considerable success in recent years, including a 90% reduction in the incidence of *P. falciparum* in Africa during the last decade^{1,79}. During this period, the incidence of *P. knowlesi* zoonosis has increased in Southeast Asia¹⁶, and a growing body of evidence suggests that monkey-to-human transmission of *P. simium* has produced malaria outbreaks in areas of Brazil where elimination had been achieved²⁰. While the public health community has traditionally ignored animal reservoirs in the context of malaria eradication, it appears that the impetus to systematically evaluate the risk of malaria zoonosis has never been greater.

Moving forward, it is critical that we adopt a holistic view of malaria zoonosis that simultaneously considers the ecological and molecular barriers to emergence. Field studies will be necessary to quantify the ecological drivers of zoonosis. In particular, longitudinal sampling of high-risk human populations, primate reservoirs, and mosquito vectors will offer measures of zoonotic incidence and exposure. These epidemiological approaches will inform and contextualize laboratory studies of host-specificity at the cellular scale. Functional approaches will benefit from the recent generation of immortalized erythroid progenitor cell lines^{132,133}, which offer genetically tractable *in vitro* culture systems for the study of host-

specificity. Finally, mathematical models of malaria zoonosis will be necessary to link transmission dynamics across these disparate scales of analysis. Without this integrated approach, efforts to elucidate the zoonotic potential of this diverse parasite clade are unlikely to be successful. Thus, it is my hope that this report will catalyze cooperation among stakeholders in the public health and scientific research communities by highlighting malaria zoonosis as a topic worthy of further consideration in the context of malaria eradication.

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